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Optimal Power Split Control for State of Charge Balancing in Battery Systems With Integrated Spatial Thermal Analysis and Aging Estimation

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an optimal control strategy for SOC balancing and introduces a framework for analyzing the spatial temperature distribution in a multi-pack battery energy storage system (BESS) composed of multiple battery modules. While various control techniques exist to distribute power among parallel-connected battery systems, their influence on the spatial temperature distribution within their modules is often neglected, despite temperature being a critical factor accelerating battery health degradation. To bridge this research gap, this framework integrates a 1D thermal simulation and state-of-health (SoH) estimation with power split control strategies. To showcase the application of this framework, a comparative study of two power-sharing methods is conducted: (i) Model Predictive Control (MPC) based State of Charge (SoC) balancing, and (ii) Rule-Based Control (RBC) strategies, highlighting their impact on temperature distribution and battery aging. Results show that MPC maintains a more uniform temperature profile, limiting peak temperatures to 300K and minimizing SoH degradation, whereas RBC results in higher peak temperatures (314K) and accelerated aging. In summary, this framework primarily intends to: (i) Enable researchers to further develop health-aware power-sharing strategies for BESS. (ii) Equip BESS operators with detailed spatial temperature insights to optimize power management and cooling systems.

1 | Introduction

Over the past decade, global energy generation has significantly diversified, with renewable energy sources contributing a substantial share. With this diversification, the need for ancillary grid services such as frequency regulation, voltage support, congestion

relief, among others, has also increased. Battery energy storage systems (BESS) are capable of effectively meeting these grid requirements by compensating mismatches in power generation and consumption, thereby ensuring grid stability and reliability [1]. Rapid decrease in lithium-ion battery costs has made BESS a crucial part of the grid infrastructure [2]. But to harness their full

Abbreviations: AC, alternating current; AI, availability index; BESS, battery energy storage system; CFD, computational fluid dynamics; DOC, depth of cycle; FDM, finite difference method; FF, fulfillment factor; FTCS, forward time central space; LFP, lithium iron phosphate; Li-NMC, lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide; MILP, mixed integer linear programming; MPC, model predictive control; OCV, open circuit voltage; SCI, self consumption increase; SOC, state of charge; SOH, state of health.

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potential, effective control strategies and advanced battery modeling are essential to maximize BESS life, efficiency, and availability to support the renewable energy integration.

State of charge (SOC) and temperature imbalances in BESS strongly affect the availability, efficiency, and life of its battery cells. SOC imbalance can greatly reduce the total capacity and cause non-uniform aging in the battery modules. On the other hand, temperature affects the lifetime of cells directly. According to Arrhenius law, the higher the operating temperatures of cells, the higher their power and capacity fading rates [3, 4]. SOC and temperature are two tightly coupled variables, but their dynamic response to changes in time creates conflicting objectives. Previous works suggested the correlations between the heat generation inside the cell as a function of its electric current, internal resistance, and the open circuit voltage (OCV) which in turn depends on cell SOC [5]. To assert the significance of their coupled nature, some works also showcased the estimation of cell SOC directly based only on their operational temperature [6]. In addition to estimating heat generation at the cell level using such correlations, understanding the dynamic response of temperature evolution spatially and temporally requires considerable understanding of the cooling conditions and thermal parameters of the material. This requires both experimental studies coupled with computational fluid dynamics (CFD) calculations [7, 8].

SOC balancing-based control strategies in BESS packs is a well-researched topic. Droop control and rule-based control suggested in the previous works achieve the desired objective of balancing SOC [9]. However, the complexity of implementing such rule-based control methodologies grows significantly with an increasing number of battery packs. This emphasizes the need to develop more robust control strategies that involve optimization techniques such as linear programming, dynamic programming, or multi-objective optimization approaches [1]. Co-balancing SOC and temperature in battery racks has also been researched in a previous work with a droop control methodology [10]. While this method can be particularly useful for real-time balancing in heterogeneous BESS units with second-life packs, estimating spatial evolution of temperature can be particularly helpful in predicting the possible non-uniform degradation at the module level inside battery packs.

The usability of model predictive control (MPC) in BESS has already been established for applications such as optimizing the operating cost of BESS, managing SOC, and balancing state of health (SOH) [11, 12]. Although prediction errors can have a negative impact on MPC performance, self-correction from the onset of BESS in each control step can counter prediction errors robustly [13]. This advantage can be used for the problem statement in this work for the balancing of SOC and for understanding the temporal behavior of the temperature. A combined approach involving optimal power split control for active temperature balancing with detailed thermal analysis can be a significant addition to the state-of-the-art thermal management systems for BESS. Previous research showcases the usefulness of a fully equipped thermal management system to reduce battery and cell degradation, but does not estimate the spatial evolution of temperatures [2].

The point-based or zero-dimensional thermal models integrated in commercial BESS digital twins manage to estimate module

level degradation using mean temperatures, but the evident non-uniformity of these temperatures depending upon the geometry of module arrangements and therefore the cooling boundary conditions can severely cause non-uniform aging of the modules within the BESS [14]. This complexity to model and integrate a thermal simulation into the thermal management system enhances even further when the cooling methodologies vary from one BESS system to another [15]. When the system configuration is defined, advanced two- or three-dimensional CFD simulations can be used to compute the spatial temperature evolution [16, 17]. But the downside of such elaborate simulations is their higher computational burden, causing a bottleneck for integration into a real-time optimal control to achieve full adaptive and predictive thermal control. In striking a balance between model precision and fast control, novel approaches using machine learning for battery temperature prediction within thermal management systems are also being researched. However, such approaches are highly dependent on measurement data up to the cell level within battery modules, which is physically challenging to obtain [18].

Therefore, combined SOC and temperature balancing with spatial thermal monitoring through simulations has been sparsely researched to date but is very relevant for a battery system that performs best in any application. In this work, we develop this approach at the pack level for a BESS use case and exploit the model's flexibility to extend its application to other use cases for any multi-pack BESS architecture. In a gist, strategically scheduling the electrical load of each battery pack to minimize the imbalances in SOC and studying the corresponding temperature imbalances both temporally and spatially is the main goal of this work.

1.1 | Paper Contributions

The scientific work presented in this paper addresses the critical aspects of power split control in BESS, including operational efficiency, throughput, system availability, heating, and degradation, as outlined below:

1. An MPC optimal power split control for SOC balancing of BESS is developed using the MILP technique with a rolling horizon of time-series input data. The optimal control strategy is then compared with three conventional control strategies derived from the literature to evaluate BESS performance.
2. A transient thermal simulation is developed to estimate the temporal and spatial evolution of temperature inside the battery packs during operation. The control strategies are coupled with this simulation model to analyze the thermal response to their power distribution.
3. The impact of control strategies on BESS aging is evaluated by analyzing the effects of SOC and temperature stress factors on battery degradation.

2 | Control and Simulation Framework

This section aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the BESS control and simulation framework developed in this

work as illustrated in Figure 1. The operation of this control framework begins with the *Power Split Control* optimization model, which takes inputs such as BESS specifications, initial states, a non-linear inverter loss model, and a forecast of the grid power profile to determine optimal power distribution set-points, P_i , and the resulting SOC_i , where i corresponds to the i^{th} battery pack. These are fed into the *Battery Equivalent Circuit Model*, which simulates battery behavior based on pack architecture, SOC-OCV relationship, and cell electrical properties, generating current, i_i , as an output. The current then serves as an input for the *Spatial Temperature Estimation* model, which incorporates battery pack geometry, thermal properties, cooling conditions, and temperature-dependent electrical resistance, $R(T)$, to predict module level temperature distribution. Finally, these outputs are used in *Aging Estimation*, which assesses battery degradation over time based on their calendric and cyclic aging.

2.1 | BESS Architecture

In this work, a BESS with two battery packs in parallel, as shown in Figure 2 is considered for the sample grid storage application. The reference battery pack is the integrated BMW SE09-N BESS with 8 modules in series [19]. Each module has 12 battery cells in the 12s1p arrangement. Each battery pack is connected to the grid through an individually controllable inverter unit. The power flow of the BESS is bidirectional through the inverter to and from the grid. The power losses during inverter operation and the thermal losses from internal heat generation, as shown in Figure 2 are accounted for in the overall energy balance. For the pack-level control of the power distribution in BESS, the SOC of the eight modules (M1–M8) of each pack is considered to be uniform.

The self consumption increase (SCI) profile shown in Figure 3 is taken from a set of publicly available BESS application

FIGURE 1 | Integrated framework for power split control and thermal simulation interfacing.

FIGURE 2 | BESS architecture modeled with two battery packs, each containing eight battery modules. The model emphasizes pack-level control, with each pack exchanging power with the grid via an inverter.

profiles [20]. This power profile is scaled by a factor of two to suit the two-pack BESS, which has a nominal power/capacity ratio of 88 kW/84 kWh, considering the electrical specifications of 120 Ah lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (Li-NMC) battery cells used in this BESS [19, 21]. The section dedicated to electro-thermal coupling in this work discusses the design parameters of the battery pack used in this work in a more detailed manner.

3 | Power Split Control Strategies

The power distribution between battery units for the balancing of SOC using linear optimization techniques, droop control, and rule-based control is a well-studied topic [12, 22]. In this section of the paper, three rule-based control strategies are compared with the MPC control strategy developed in this work to balance the SOC of the battery packs in BESS. To make comparisons, four performance indices, namely, fulfillment factor (FF), availability index (AI), inverter efficiency (η_{inv}) and battery efficiency (η_b) are defined and evaluated. FF is the ratio of the total power supplied by BESS to the total input power of the grid for the duration of the operation, as shown in Equation (1).

$$FF = \left(\frac{\sum_{t=0}^n (|P_{AC1}(t)| + |P_{AC2}(t)|)}{\sum_{t=0}^n |P_{grid}(t)|} \right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where:

$P_{AC[i]}$ is the AC throughput power of battery pack - i ,

P_{grid} is the input grid power,

t is time,

n is the total number of time steps.

The AC power of each battery pack ranges from 0 to the nominal power of each pack (88 kW) depending on its available energy capacity and the grid demand. The absolute values of the powers are considered for computing total throughput and total input powers, as the system is modeled to be bi-directional, allowing both charging and discharging independently in each battery

FIGURE 3 | SCI derived power profile for 30 days from standard battery application profiles [20].

pack. AI calculates the availability of the system against the grid demand during the operation of BESS. This implies that AI counts the number of time instances in which the available capacity of BESS met the power requests from the grid relative to its total number of power requests, as explained in Equation (2). A 100% AI suggests that the available capacity of the system allows it to support the grid throughout the operation.

$$AI = \left(\frac{\text{No. of fulfilled power requests}}{\text{Total power requests from grid}} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The inverter loss curve as shown in Figure 4 is modeled as a combination of five piecewise linear functions to compute the relative loss with respect to the power throughput of the inverter and battery pack combination. At close to zero throughput power of the pack, the losses amount to approximately 0.75% of the nominal unit power and 2.85% at the full nominal power [9]. The corresponding inverter efficiency (η_{inv}) for the entire operation of BESS can be calculated as presented in Equation (3).

$$\eta_{inv} = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{t=0}^n (P_{loss1}(t) + P_{loss2}(t))}{\sum_{t=0}^n (|P_{AC1}(t)| + |P_{AC2}(t)|)} \right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where:

$P_{loss[i]}$ is the inverter loss through battery pack - i

Battery efficiency (η_b) is another important performance indicator for the control strategies studied in this work. During the operation of a battery cell, heat is generated from within due to the internal resistance to the flow of electric current within the cell as defined in Equations (5) and (6). This heat corresponds to the power loss in both the charge and discharge scenarios. Additionally, this heat depending upon the cooling power affects the core temperature of the battery cells leading to a variation in their internal resistance as shown in the Figure A1 [23]. In later sections of this work dealing with spatial temperature estimation, the resistance of each battery module is estimated as a function of temperature using the piecewise linear functions derived from Figure A1. Considering this temperature dependency of internal resistance, the battery efficiency of the BESS can be calculated as shown in Equation (4).

FIGURE 4 | Inverter loss curve approximated as a piecewise linear function from experimental data [5].

$$\eta_b = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{t=0}^n (\dot{Q}_{\text{pack1}}(t) + \dot{Q}_{\text{pack2}}(t))}{\sum_{t=0}^n (|P_{\text{AC1}}(t)| + |P_{\text{AC2}}(t)|)} \right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{pack1}}(t) = (i_{\text{pack1}}(t))^2 \cdot R_{\text{pack1}} \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{pack2}}(t) = (i_{\text{pack2}}(t))^2 \cdot R_{\text{pack2}} \quad (6)$$

where:

$\dot{Q}_{\text{pack}[i]}$ is the heat generation in battery pack - i ,

$i_{\text{pack}[i]}$ is the electric current in battery pack - i ,

$R_{\text{pack}[i]}$ is the total internal resistance of battery pack - i .

3.1 | Model Predictive Control

The MPC controller developed in this work is formulated as a rolling-horizon MILP to solve the power split optimization problem for a multi-pack BESS [24]. For simplicity, a two-battery-pack BESS, as illustrated in Figure 2, is considered to compare against the rule-based control strategies in the following sections. The optimization model estimates SOC by calculating the energy content of the battery packs using their throughput power (P_{AC}), inverter power loss (P_{loss}) and the power loss due to heat generation (\dot{Q}_{pack}). This computation for the charging scenario is shown as an illustration in Equation (9) [25, 26]. The constraints on the state and control variables, SOC and P_{AC} respectively, are shown in Equation (7) and Equation (8). While the auxiliary variables P_{loss} and \dot{Q}_{pack} are calculated as explained in the previous section, the derived variable, P_{charge} , responsible for the SOC estimation is computed as shown in Equation (10). A hard constraint is imposed to ensure that the battery storage system meets the total power demand from the grid, as expressed in Equation (11).

The grid SCI profile is processed using a rolling horizon approach, optimizing over a 9-h prediction horizon and applying the first 3 h as the control horizon. At each iteration, the optimal power setpoints are recorded, and the next prediction begins at the end of the control horizon, progressing in 3-h steps until the entire grid profile in Figure 3 is covered. The optimization achieves SOC balance between both packs with different initial states. Thereafter, the power split between the packs is even to ensure uniform SOC across the packs.

$$0.1 \leq \text{SOC}_{[i]}(t) \leq 0.9 \quad (7)$$

$$0 \leq |P_{\text{AC}[i]}(t)| \leq P_{\text{nominal}[i]} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{SOC}_{[i]}(t) = \text{SOC}_{[i]}(t-1) + \frac{P_{\text{charge}[i]}(t) \cdot \Delta t}{\text{Capacity}_{\text{pack}[i]}} \quad (9)$$

$$P_{\text{AC}[i]}(t) = P_{\text{charge}[i]}(t) + P_{\text{loss}[i]}(t) + \dot{Q}_{\text{pack}[i]}(t) \quad (10)$$

$$P_{\text{grid}}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m P_{\text{AC}[i]}(t) \quad (11)$$

$$\text{SOC}_{\text{mean}}(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (\text{SOC}_{[i]}(t))}{m} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Objective} = \min \left(\sum_{t=0}^n \sum_{i=1}^m |\text{SOC}_{\text{mean}}(t) - \text{SOC}_{[i]}(t)| \right) \quad (13)$$

where:

Capacity_{pack[i]} is the of battery pack nominal capacity,

Δt is the time step size.

SOC _{i} is the SOC of battery pack - i ,

SOC_{mean} is the mean SOC of all packs,

m is the total number of of battery packs.

In this MILP formulation, a binary variable is introduced to model P_{Loss} by capturing the switching behavior between zero and non-zero pack throughput power, P_{AC} as depicted in Figure 4. The overall objective function of this optimization problem as shown in Equation (13) is to balance the SOC during operation and to maintain all packs at an uniform SOC after balancing.

The optimal power split obtained from this MPC control strategy causes the SOC variation in the battery packs as shown in Figure 5a. The results clearly demonstrate the SOC balancing behavior achieved with the MPC optimizer. For 30-day BESS operation using the MPC optimal power split control, the fulfillment factor is 100% and the availability index is 100% while the inverter and battery efficiencies are 92.9% and 98%, respectively. In the next subsection, we compare this optimal control for SOC balancing against three rule-based control strategies for its operational performance and availability.

3.2 | Rule Based Control

Rule based control governs the operation of a BESS by implementing a set of predefined rules or logic to control the charging and discharging of the battery units. These logics are usually associated with the BESS operation parameters such as threshold SOC, load forecasting, grid signals, renewable energy integration, or time-of-use (ToU) tariffs. In this work, the focus is on three rule-based control strategies, two of which govern the operation of BESS based on SOC thresholds, and the third aims to improve the energy efficiency of the system.

3.2.1 | Even Power Split Strategy

This benchmark control strategy evenly distributes the grid power demand between both the packs within the usable SOC limits, set in this work as (0.1, 0.9) as shown in Equation (14). In the scenario where one or both batteries breach the safety limits,

FIGURE 5 | Comparison between control strategies for SOC balancing after 30 days.

the BESS switches off from the grid and awaits its power demand signal in the next time step, as shown in Equation (15). For the 30-day input profile, the FF obtained for this control strategy is 99.3% and the AI is 99.7%. The inverter and battery efficiencies are 93.1% and 97.6%, respectively.

$$P_{AC1}(t) = P_{AC2}(t) = \frac{P_{grid}(t)}{2}, \text{ for } t: 1 \rightarrow n \quad (14)$$

if $SOC_1(t)$ and $SOC_2(t) \in [0.1, 0.9]$

$$P_{AC1}(t) = P_{AC2}(t) = 0, \text{ for } t: 1 \rightarrow n \quad (15)$$

if $SOC_1(t)$ or $SOC_2(t) \notin [0.1, 0.9]$

Figure 5b shows the SOC evolution of the two battery packs during operation. Pack-1 reaches the upper safety limit of the SOC, making the whole system unavailable until the next discharge request.

3.2.2 | Consecutive Power Split Strategy: Active (+Backup) Pack

This benchmark control primarily operates the active battery pack based on threshold-based operation until SOC reaches the lower or upper limits, set to 0.1 and 0.9, respectively, as shown in Equation (16). Upon reaching the threshold, a simple control rule activates the backup pack for operation while maintaining the active pack in its current state, as shown in Equation (17). The operation of the active pack is prioritized over that of the backup pack at every control action to charge

or discharge during operation. When both the packs reach the threshold, the BESS switches off from the grid, as shown in Equation (18). For the designated capacity of both the packs and the grid input profile of 30 days, FF for this strategy is 100% and AI is 100%. The inverter and battery efficiencies are 93.3% and 95.1%, respectively.

$$P_{AC1}(t) = P_{grid}(t), \text{ for } t: 1 \rightarrow n, \text{ if } SOC_1(t) \in [0.1, 0.9] \quad (16)$$

$$P_{AC2}(t) = P_{grid}(t), \text{ for } t: 1 \rightarrow n, \quad (17)$$

if $SOC_1(t) \notin [0.1, 0.9]$ and $SOC_2(t) \in [0.1, 0.9]$.

$$P_{AC1}(t) = P_{AC2}(t) = 0, \text{ for } t: 1 \rightarrow n, \quad (18)$$

if $SOC_i(t) \notin [0.1, 0.9] \forall i \in \{1, 2\}$

The corresponding SOC levels obtained from this strategy are shown in Figure 5c. It is evident that pack-1 reaches its threshold and the control activates pack-2 in order to meet the requested power of the grid. Pack-2 participates only during charging, while pack-1 discharges and charges to its upper threshold of the state of energy.

3.2.3 | Power Flow Distribution Strategy for Improved Inverter Efficiency

This power flow distribution strategy was originally developed for a utility-scale battery storage system and aims to

improve the energy efficiency of the system by minimizing power electronics losses during operation [9]. For the sake of comparative analysis, this strategy is modified by adding strict thresholds on SOC to be between (0.1, 0.9) similar to the strategies earlier.

In the course of this work, this control strategy will be referred to as *Rule Based Control*. This control strategy maximizes the usage of packs individually and alternatively at their full load to reduce the dominant power electronic loads at partial loads. A droop control logic activates both batteries for scenarios where the demand grid power exceeds the nominal power of the individual packs. Figure 5d shows the SOC evolution of the two battery packs during operation [9]. For a 30-day operation, the FF for this strategy is 100% and the AI is 100%. The inverter and battery efficiencies are 93.2% and 97.6% respectively.

4 | Electro-Thermal Coupling

The Rint equivalent circuit model is used to obtain the correlation between the open circuit voltage (V_{ocv}) of battery cells and their terminal voltage ($V_{terminal,cell}$) as shown in Equation (19) [27]. SOC profiles of the battery packs obtained from the control strategies are used to calculate the V_{ocv} of the battery cells using the SOC-OCV curve shown Appendix A, Figure A2 [28]. The computed mean V_{ocv} of the battery cells in both battery packs is presented in Figure 6.

$$V_{terminal,cell}(t) = V_{ocv}(t) - i_{cell}(t) \cdot R_{cell} \quad (19)$$

$$i_{cell}(t) = \frac{P_{AC}(t)}{n_{pack} \cdot V_{terminal,cell}(t)} \quad (20)$$

$$V_{terminal,pack}(t) = n_{pack} \cdot V_{terminal,cell}(t) \quad (21)$$

The mean terminal voltage for the battery packs is then derived using the throughput power profiles obtained from each control strategy, P_{AC1} and P_{AC2} . The electric currents at the cell level (i_{cell}) in the equivalent circuit can be substituted using Equation (20). This substitution solves the ($V_{terminal,cell}$) which then can be scaled up to the pack level as shown in Equation (21).

SOC and temperature influence the internal resistance of the battery cells. In lithium ion cells, at lower temperatures,

their internal resistance is typically found to be higher and vice versa [29]. In this section, to compute the $V_{terminal,cell}$, an initial R_{cell} value of 2 m Ω is considered under ambient conditions [23]. This value is further adjusted for each control strategy using the temperature-dependent R_{cell} values, which are based on the estimated operating temperatures from the thermal simulation. The electric currents are computed using the equivalent resistance in a 12s1p arrangement of cells in a battery module. This current remains uniform across the series connected modules of the pack as shown in Figure 7. This methodology to compute currents is validated with respect to the industry system using an experimental power profile for battery cycling and the resulting currents obtained are plotted in the Appendix A, Figure A3.

The heat dissipation during the operation of BESS as a result of this electric current and the equivalent internal resistance of the cells is the source of heat generation for the thermal model discussed below.

4.1 | Thermal Simulation

Finite difference method (FDM) is an effective numerical solution of a large class of transient thermal diffusion problems [30]. Although the general limitation could be an inaccurate approximation of the actual geometry using regular mesh construction, the FDM model developed in this work, approximating the geometry of the pack into a one-dimensional (1D) mesh, can be used as a good starting point for the estimation of the spatial temperature along the battery pack. Figure 8 illustrates the arrangement of battery modules and their interaction with ambient air inside the battery pack. The symmetry in this arrangement, highlighted by the shaded and non-shaded areas, is leveraged to simplify the spatial thermal model for 1D simulation. This symmetry implies that the 1D spatial temperature distribution in modules M1 to M4 is identical to that in modules M5 to M8. In this study, the 1D thermal simulation focuses on the non-shaded region containing modules M1 to M4 to analyze their spatial temperature evolution under different control strategies.

Figure 9 illustrates the concept of 1D heat flow through modules M1 to M4 used in the simulation model. The modules are modeled with heat generation (\dot{q}) due to electrical internal resistance (R_{cell}) and can conduct heat within and with their neighboring

FIGURE 6 | Variation of open circuit voltage of battery cells in packs as a function of their SOC in MPC control.

FIGURE 7 | Electric currents derived from the MPC control for the first 6 days of operation.

modules. R_{conv} is the convective thermal resistance from modules M1 and M4 to the ambient air. The conductive resistance inside the modules, $R_{cond,1}$ is different from that between the modules, $R_{cond,2}$. Equation (22) approximates 1D heat diffusion in the pack with the modules modeled as the heat generation sources selectively activated at their location in the pack. Equation (23) calculates the volumetric specific heat generation from the modules where their internal resistance is modeled as a function of temperature as explained in Equation (24). Equation (25) models the convective heat transfer to a constant ambient temperature (T_{air}). This boundary condition offers natural convective cooling at both ends of each pack. For simplicity, the thermal parameters of the system as shown in Table 1 are considered constant with temperature.

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \kappa \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \dot{q} \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{q} = \frac{i_{cell}^2 \cdot R_{module}}{\text{volume}_{module}} \quad (23)$$

$$R_{module} = n_{module} \cdot R_{cell}(T) \quad (24)$$

$$-\kappa \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = h \cdot (T_{air} - T) \quad (25)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{\kappa}{\rho \cdot C} \quad (26)$$

$$\alpha \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta x)^2} < \frac{1}{2} \quad (27)$$

where:

T is spatial temperature of the pack,

T_{air} is ambient temperature,

t is time,

x is spatial coordinate,

ρ is average cell density,

C is specific heat capacity,

κ is thermal conductivity,

R_{module} is module internal resistance,

R_{cell} is temperature dependent cell resistance,

n_{module} is number of cells in module as in Table 1,

volume_{module} is product of L, B, H as in Table 11,

\dot{q} is specific heat generation from R_{module} .

FIGURE 8 | Model reduction for thermal simulation considering symmetry inside battery pack.

Forward time central space (FTCS), finite difference scheme is used with a 1D computational mesh along the length of the pack to compute its temperature evolution during operation. The stability of the solution of this second-order centered difference in space and first-order difference in time has been ensured by tuning the time step size (Δt) and mesh nodal spaces (Δx) along with the constant thermal diffusivity (α) as defined in Equation (26). Equation (27) presents the stability criteria with the FTCS scheme [32]. The applicability of this spatial thermal simulation on this industrial BESS is validated and showcased in the Appendix A, Figure A4.

As an illustration, the temperature evolution of battery pack-1 using the *Consecutive Power Split Strategy* is shown in Figure 10. This pack shows a significant temperature rise, peaking at 314K, reflecting its active role in supporting grid demands, as shown in Figure 5c. As a result, greater heat is generated within its modules. In the next subsection, thermal simulation results for each strategy are compared to identify the thermally optimal power split control approach under identical grid load and cooling conditions.

FIGURE 9 | Thermal network for 1D transient thermal simulation.

TABLE 1 | Design parameters of the BESS with integrated BMW SE09-N battery pack consisting of NMC-622 cells used for system modeling and simulation [19].

Parameter	Value	Unit
Modules per pack	8	
Cells per module (n_{module})	12	
Cells per pack (n_{pack})	96	
Battery pack length	1.66	m
Battery module length (L)	0.4	m
Battery module width (B)	0.32	m
Battery module height (H)	0.176	m
Module nominal voltage (V_{module})	43.92	V
Module nominal capacity	5.3	kWh
Cell type capacity	120	Ah
Cell density (ρ) [7]	3300	kg m ⁻³
Specific heat capacity (C) [31]	1100	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Thermal conductivity (κ) [31]	0.5	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Convective coefficient (h) [2]	16	W m ⁻² K ⁻¹
Pack initial temperature	298	K
Ambient temperature (T_{air})	295	K

FIGURE 10 | Spatial temperature evolution of Pack-1 using consecutive power split strategy.

4.2 | Spatial Temperature Estimation

In Figure 11, for the *MPC Control Strategy* and the *Consecutive Power Split Strategy*, the M2 module of pack-1 and pack-2 are plotted for their temperature growth during the 30-day operation. Adjacently, the spatial temperature distribution of both these packs is presented. This visual representation also aims

to explain the passive thermal balancing nature of power split control strategies. For the same initial temperatures of both the packs, it is evident from Figure 11a,c that *MPC Control* achieved a more balanced temperature evolution throughout its operation compared to the *Consecutive Control*. This passive balancing of temperature across packs is a direct implication of the SOC balance achieved during its operation, as shown in Figure 5a. On the other hand, Figure 11a presenting the temperature evolution of M2 modules in *Consecutive Control* shows a large temperature imbalance between the packs in accordance with its non-uniform power distribution strategy.

At the end of the 30-day operation, the estimated temperatures in the packs are plotted along their length in Figure 11b,d. Due to the imbalanced power distribution throughout its operation, *Consecutive Control* develops the highest temperature growth, with a maximum temperature of its M2 module reaching up to 314 K. For its optimal approach toward balancing the SOC, thereby employing both packs of BESS uniformly after balancing, *MPC Control* generates the lowest temperature growth, with its M2 module reaching up to 300.5 K. This analysis shows the importance of the uniform operation of BESS packs for a thermally balanced operation, given the initial temperatures are uniform for the packs. With the *MPC Control* developed in this work, these two conditions are fulfilled, where it achieves the temperature balance passively.

This spatial thermal analysis can be used to estimate the temperature evolution of the modules of interest and to further estimate their temperature dependent electrical and thermal parameters. Although the thermal parameters mentioned in Table 1 are considered constant with temperature, the electrical internal resistance (R_{cell}) is estimated as a function of the cell temperature during the thermal simulation in this work. The internal resistance of Li-NMC cells presented in Figure A1 is modeled as a set of piecewise linear functions in this thermal simulation to estimate the actual temperature dependent internal resistance. Using the temperature evolution of the M2 module of pack-1 for each control strategy as shown in Figure 12, its mean internal resistance (R_{cell}) is estimated for this temperature range. As an illustration, for the *MPC Control* and the *Consecutive Control* it is estimated to be 2.4 m Ω and 1.92 m Ω respectively. These mean resistances are used in the equivalent circuit model to calculate the cell terminal voltage ($V_{\text{terminal,cell}}$) and current (i_{cell}) in Section 4.

In order to further assert the importance of SOC and temperature balancing, in the next section, this analysis is further extended to compare these control strategies on the grounds of battery aging.

5 | Aging Estimation

This section aims to estimate the aging associated with the 30-day operation of BESS using each control strategy discussed in this work. The two operational parameters of interest, SOC and temperature, are analyzed to determine their stress on the aging of the system. In the previous section, Figure 12 presented the temperature evolution of the M2 module. Similarly, Figure 13 represents the SOC levels of M2 in each strategy. From the perspective of calendar aging, it is essential to determine the mean SOC levels during the BESS operation [33].

FIGURE 11 | Comparison between control strategies for temporal temperature evolution and spatial distribution after 30 days.

FIGURE 12 | Comparison of M2 module temperature evolution using different control strategies.

For the *MPC Control*, the average SOC for pack-1 is 0.59, while this value accounts for 0.81, 0.76, and 0.63 with the *Even Power Split*, *Consecutive Control*, and *Rule-Based Control*, respectively.

In Figure 14 the degradation effects of the M2 module of pack-1 for each control strategy are plotted. The drop in SOH has been calculated based on the SOC profile and the temperature evolution of M2 presented in Figure 12. SimSES is used to calculate the capacity loss induced by both calendric and cyclic aging for the 30-day operating patterns [34].

The aging models for Li-NMC cells as shown in Equations (28) and (30) present the capacity calculations under calendar and cyclic aging respectively. The aging behavior for new batteries is dominated by calendar aging and for the given SOC profiles it is mainly influenced by the module's lifetime and its level of SOC and temperature during operation [35]. The calendar aging effects imposed by the lifetime are the same for all strategies. This

FIGURE 13 | Comparison of SOC of M2 module using different control strategies.

FIGURE 14 | Comparison of SOH loss of M2 module using different control strategies for 30-day operation.

means that the differences in degradation are determined by the aging factor, α_{cap} , which is a function of the cell voltage and temperature as shown in Equation (29) [35]. And cell voltage is

directly correlated with its SOC as discussed in Section 4. The *MPC Control* shows a lower SOC level during operation compared to the other strategies as shown in Figure 13. Similarly, the temperature evolution of the M2 module in each strategy as presented in Figure 12 also suggests a lower temperature stress compared to the other rule-based control strategies. This contributes to an overall lower α_{cap} . This can be evidently seen from Figure 14 that the capacity degradation imposed by the *MPC Control* is less compared to the other rule-based control strategies.

$$C_{\text{cal}} = 1 - \alpha_{\text{cap}} \cdot t^{0.75} \quad (28)$$

$$\alpha_{\text{cap}}(T, V) = (7.543 \cdot V - 23.75) \cdot 10^6 \cdot e^{-6976/T} \quad (29)$$

$$C_{\text{cyc}} = 1 - \beta_{\text{cap}} \cdot \sqrt{Q} \quad (30)$$

$$\beta_{\text{cap}} = 7.348 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (\phi V - 3.667)^2 + 7.600 \cdot 10^{-4} + 4.081 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot D_{\text{DOD}} \quad (31)$$

where:

C_{cal} is the capacity due to calendar aging,

t is the operation time,

α_{cap} is the calendar aging factor,

C_{cyc} is the capacity due to cyclic aging,

β_{cap} is the cycle aging factor,

Q is the through put energy,

ϕV is the quadratic average voltage, and

D_{DOD} is the cycle depth.

6 | Discussions

Table 2 compares each control strategy against their performance indices FF, AI, inverter and battery efficiencies, η_{inv} and η_{b} , and their key operational parameters such as the maximum temperature in the pack T_{max} , mean SOC levels of pack-1, $\text{SOC}_{1,\text{mean}}$ and SOH of module, M2, in pack-1, SOH . It is apparent that the *Consecutive Control* gains the maximum temperature in the pack owing to the prioritization of usage of one battery pack.

Due to a high SOC level and higher temperature development, the drop of SOH is maximum in this strategy. While the *Even Power Split* achieves temperature balancing across the packs, its FF and AI are lower, indicating its lower reliability and operational unavailability. On the other hand, its temperature growth and SOH are comparable to that of the *MPC Control*. When it comes to the *Rule Based Control* modeled for the improved electronic efficiency, the inverter efficiency for its operational duration is the highest among the control strategies. Its performance on the basis of SOH and T_{max} is comparable to the *MPC Control* but under performs in its battery efficiency.

Due to the well-constrained optimization model programmed in its rolling horizon framework, *MPC Control* achieves SOC balancing and 100% FF and AI. The optimization also achieves the SOC balancing in the minimum possible time which ensures even power distribution in both the packs after balancing. This in turn results in a higher battery efficiency during its operation. As the SOC level and the maximum temperature, T_{max} , are the lowest among the control strategies, the SOH of the BESS is the highest for the 30 day operation. This study infers that prioritizing SOC balance aids in achieving higher availability of the BESS thereby also achieving the temperature balance passively. But in-order to achieve and maintain the SOC balance at all time, the control operates both the packs at partial loads thereby losing some power during the inverter conversions. Additionally, it is also observed from the thermal simulations that although the temperatures are balanced at the pack level, in each pack the central modules, M2 and M3, are hotter than the boundary modules due to the passive air cooling model used in this work. This can create heterogeneity in the aging of the modules. To understand this temperature imbalance in the modules, the *MPC Control* and the corresponding thermal analysis is further extended for a longer simulation keeping the same

FIGURE 15 | Temperature evolution of all modules in the battery pack-1 using MPC control strategy after 120 days.

TABLE 2 | Performance evaluation of control strategies based on their fulfillment factor (FF), availability index (AI), inverter conversion efficiency (η_{inv}), battery efficiency (η_{b}), maximum temperature in the pack (T_{max}), mean SOC of pack-1 ($\text{SOC}_{1,\text{mean}}$), and SOH of M2 in pack-1 (SOH).

Control strategy	FF (%)	AI (%)	η_{inv} (%)	η_{b} (%)	T_{max} (K)	$\text{SOC}_{1,\text{mean}}$	SOH
Even power split	99.3	99.7	93.1	97.6	302	0.81	99.962
Consecutive power split	100	100	93.2	95.1	314	0.76	99.939
Rule based power split	100	100	93.3	97.6	301.9	0.63	99.963
Model predictive control	100	100	92.9	98.5	300.5	0.59	99.966

cooling conditions to understand the temperature evolution of each module for 120 days grid SCI profile. The results as shown in Figure 15 indicate that over longer periods of operation, although both the packs have the same temperature profile similar to Figure 11c, the modules heat up differently with the M2 and M3 modules being the hotter. To negate this imbalance, alongside the pack level control, a secondary level control to operate the modules individually can be deployed [36, 37].

7 | Conclusions

This paper proposes an approach to integrate an SOC balancing optimal power-split control with a 1D transient thermal simulation model for pack-level controlled BESS units. To achieve SOC balancing across the battery packs, a rolling-horizon MILP approach is employed within an MPC framework to determine the control actions. The outputs from this optimization framework serve as inputs to the transient thermal simulation, which provides insights into the spatial temperature evolution within each battery pack of the BESS unit during operation.

Additionally, a comparative analysis is performed with three rule-based control strategies derived from the literature, integrated with the same thermal model. The results indicate that the MPC strategy achieves simultaneous balancing of SOC and temperature across the packs, while also delivering superior performance in terms of overall energy throughput, system availability, lower temperature rise, and reduced SOH degradation. However, the inverter efficiency of the MPC strategy is slightly lower compared to the rule-based control dedicated to maximizing efficiency.

The integrated model is further extended to study the thermal behavior over an extended operational duration. Findings suggest that while the MPC control strategy effectively co-balances SOC and temperature at the pack level, temperature disparities emerge among the modules within each pack by the end of the operation. This highlights the necessity for module-level power distribution control to achieve holistic SOC and temperature balancing within BESS units. Finally, this approach can be expanded to incorporate active cooling methodologies, such as fan or liquid cooling, to evaluate system performance based on overall energy consumption and to investigate the uniformity of spatial temperature distribution within battery packs.

Author Contributions

Vivek Teja Tanjavooru: methodology, software, visualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing. **Melina Graner:** visualization, writing – original draft. **Prashant Pant:** writing – review and editing. **Thomas Hamacher:** supervision, writing – review. **Holger Hesse:** supervision, writing – review and editing.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Appendix A

Figure A1 illustrates the temperature dependency of internal resistance in a battery cell. As shown, the internal resistance decreases with increasing temperature. This inverse relationship reflects the typical electrochemical behavior of battery cells—higher temperatures enhance ion mobility, thereby reducing resistance [23]. This correlation is utilized in calculating the cell's internal resistance by considering the estimated temperature from the spatial thermal analysis.

Figure A2 illustrates the relationship between the SOC and the OCV during charge and discharge for the NMC battery cells [28]. This correlation is used to derive the OCV of the cells using the SOC values estimated from the power split control strategies.

FIGURE A1 | Li-NMC internal resistance as a function of temperature interpreted from experimental study [23].

FIGURE A2 | SOC-OCV curve for NMC battery interpreted from experimental study [28].

FIGURE A3 | Comparison of electric current obtained from equivalent circuit simulation versus the experiment.

FIGURE A4 | Simulated module core temperature versus measured pack surface temperature.

In this work, a validation study has been conducted for the spatial thermal simulation using industry-acquired data. The dataset is based on an experimental usage profile involving charge and discharge cycling between the minimum and maximum state of charge, providing a valuable benchmark. However, it is important to note that the data only includes the minimum and maximum recorded surface temperatures of the pack, without detailed information on sensor placement. Figure A3 presents a comparison between the experimentally measured currents and the simulated results, demonstrating a strong overall agreement.

Figure A4 compares the measured surface temperatures of the battery pack with the simulated internal temperatures at the module level. While both the temperature profiles follow a similar trend, the surface temperatures are lower than the simulated core temperatures as the surface is more exposed to the ambient air cooling. Acquiring internal temperature data for the battery pack experimentally presents a significant challenge, which motivates the development of the spatial thermal model presented in this manuscript as these temperature differences between the pack surface and the core contribute to inhomogeneous aging at the module level.